

Supplementary Material

A How to Read a Conditional Intensity Matrix

Reading a CIM can be tricky. For example, let \mathcal{G} be a directed graph with three vertices $\mathbf{V} = \{X, Y, Z\}$, connected as depicted in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: The graph \mathcal{G} .

Fig. 2: Generic CIM $\mathbf{Q}_{X_i|\Pi_i}$ representation.

If \mathcal{G} is the graph of a CTBN, then each vertex in \mathbf{V} is mapped to a random variable in \mathbf{X} , which in turn is parametrized by a CIM. Figure 2 represents the layout of a generic CIM $\mathbf{Q}_{X_i|\Pi_i}$. In this example, the three random variables have the following domains: $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, $Y = \{0, 1\}$ and $Z = \{0, 1\}$. When we set $Y = 0$ and $Z = 1$ the corresponding IM $\mathbf{Q}_{X|\{Y=0, Z=1\}}$ is represented as depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Specific IM $\mathbf{Q}_{X|\{Y=0, Z=1\}}$ representation.

If we set $X = 1$ then the row $\mathbf{Q}_{X=1|\{Y=0,Z=1\}}$ encodes both the exponential distribution modeling the expected transition time and the categorical distribution of the next state. Figure 4 depicts in blue q_i and the corresponding probability density function (PDF) of the exponential $\text{Exp}(q_i)$, while in red $\theta_{ij} = q_{ij}/q_i, i \neq j$ and the corresponding distribution $\text{Cat}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_i)$.

Fig. 4: Exponential and categorical distributions for $\mathbf{Q}_{X=1|\{Y=0,Z=1\}}$.

For example, here $q_{ii} = -2.714$ means that the parameter of the exponential distribution is $\lambda = q_i = -q_{ii} = 2.714$, with an expected transition time of $\mathbb{E}[\text{Exp}(\lambda)] = 1/\lambda = 0.3685$. Let's say time is measured in hours, then with $\{Y = 0, Z = 1\}$ the variable $X = 1$ is expected to transition out of the current x_1 in 0.3685 hours, or 22.11 minutes. Moreover, X will transition to 0 with probability $q_{ij}/q_i = 1.263/2.714 = 0.4653$.

B Parameter Learning from Incomplete Trajectories

In real world settings it is unlikely to fully observe every variable all the time.

Expectation-Maximization. A more realistic approach is to estimate the *expected* sufficient statistics $\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ijk}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{T}}_{ij}$ from an *incomplete* trajectory σ^- via the expectation-maximization (EM) [1] algorithm:

0. Initialize the current parameters $\mathbf{Q}_{X_i|\Pi_i}^0$ arbitrarily.
1. *Expectation step:* with the current k -th parameters, use σ^- as evidence to generate a *completed* trajectory σ^+ and compute $\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ijk}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{T}}_{ij}$ from σ^+ .
2. *Maximization step:* estimate the next $(k+1)$ -th parameters from $\bar{\mathbf{N}}_{ijk}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{T}}_{ij}$ as if they were computed from a complete trajectory.
3. Check convergence using a stopping criterion, e.g. absolute difference from k -th and $(k+1)$ -th parameters or maximum number of iterations. If no convergence is reached, then go to (1), otherwise return the current parameters.

The difficult part of the EM algorithm is the expectation step: completing a partially-observed trajectory is not a trivial task.

Importance Sampling. A method to sample a completed trajectory σ^+ from the evidence \mathbf{e} contained in the incomplete trajectory σ^- is given by the Importance Sampling [2] algorithm, which generates a set of weighted trajectories compatible with \mathbf{e} , as depicted in Figure 5. Since the trajectories are drawn from a proposal distribution P' consistent with \mathbf{e} , each σ_i^+ is weighted by the likelihood of the evidence $\omega(\sigma_i^+) = P(\sigma_i^+, \mathbf{e})/P'(\sigma_i^+)$, and the expected sufficient statistics are computed as a weighted average over $\omega(\sigma_i^+)$.

Fig. 5: Evidence coming from the incomplete trajectory σ^- can be point-wise, transition-like or interval-like. More than one completed trajectory σ^+ generated via importance sampling, such as σ_1^+ and σ_2^+ , is compatible with the same σ^- .

Uncertain Evidence. In the context of event-based data, evidence comes in many forms. It can happen that there is uncertainty about the exact status in which a variable is at a specific point in time due to contrasting information coming from different data sources. To deal with this kind of uncertainty even the evidence must be treated as uncertain. Luckily, importance sampling is flexible enough to accommodate for uncertain evidence [3] without changing the whole theoretical framework.

C Structure Learning from Incomplete Trajectories

As EM learn the parameters of a CTBN from incomplete trajectories, the only remaining piece to construct a CTBN from data is to learn its graph.

Structural Expectation-Maximization. Learning a graph from incomplete trajectories can be done via the structural EM (SEM) [4] algorithm:

0. Initialize the current graph \mathcal{G}^0 and parameters $\mathbf{Q}_{X_i|\Pi_i}^0$ arbitrarily.
1. *Expectation step:* with the current k -th graph and parameters, use σ^- as evidence for the EM algorithm to generate a completed trajectory σ^+ .
2. *Maximization step:* estimate the next $(k + 1)$ -th graph using σ^+ and the prior knowledge \mathcal{K} as input for a structure learning algorithm.
3. Check convergence using a stopping criterion, e.g. absolute difference from k -th and $(k + 1)$ -th graph and/or parameters, or maximum number of iterations. If no convergence is reached, then go to (1), otherwise return the current solution.

Causal Discovery. The structure learning task can be constrained by experts' knowledge for two distinct purposes: (i) to speed up the learning step, by discarding irrelevant edges or forcing them in place, thus skipping the independence checks altogether, and (ii) to add a causal interpretation of it, making it not only a predictive model but also a causal model, capable of explaining the interplay between the observed variables. In this sense, while structure learning aims to construct a model for its inference capability, the causal discovery task serves as a tool to investigate an understudied problem, where the resulting model makes the cause-effect relationships explicit.

D CENTER-TBI Categorical Levels

Table 1: Categorical levels of selected variables.

Variable	Levels
HVICP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (0, 15] - ICP lower or equal to 15 mmHg. - (15, 20] - ICP between 15 and 20 mmHg. - (20, 25] - ICP between 20 and 25 mmHg. - (25, +∞) - ICP higher than 15 mmHg.
HosComplEventHypocapnia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0 - No episodes, - 1 - Single episode, - 2 - Multiple episodes.
MarshallCTClassification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 - No visible pathology on CT, - 2 - Cisterns present, MLS < 5 mm, - 3 - Cisterns compressed or absent, MLS < 5 mm, - 4 - MLS > 5 mm, no mass lesion > 25 cc, - 5 - Evacuated mass lesion, - 6 - Non-evacuated mass lesion.
TILCSFDrainage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0 - No, - 1 - Yes.
TILFever	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0 - No, - 1 - Yes.
TILHyperosmolarTherapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0 - No, - 1 - Yes.
TILHyperventilation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0 - No, - 1 - Yes.
TILMannitolDose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0 - No mannitol dose. - (0, 2] - Total mannitol dose lower or equal to 2g. - (2, +∞) - Total mannitol dose higher than 2g.
TILSedation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0 - No, - 1 - Yes.

E Prior Knowledge Elicitation

To guide the causal discovery procedure, prior knowledge on the interaction mechanism between ICP and treatments is encoded as required edges in Table 2.

Table 2: Required edges elicited from experts knowledge.

Required Edges	Description
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HVICP} \\ \Leftrightarrow \\ \text{HosComplEventHypocapnia} \end{array}$	Elevated ICP is often managed with hyperventilation, which lowers PaCO ₂ and can lead to hypocapnia; hypocapnia causes vasoconstriction, reducing ICP.
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HVICP} \\ \Leftrightarrow \\ \text{MarshallCTClassification} \end{array}$	Severe CT abnormalities are associated with higher ICP; persistent intracranial hypertension can also worsen injury progression detectable on CT.
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HVICP} \\ \Leftrightarrow \\ \text{TILCSFDrainage} \end{array}$	CSF drainage is used to lower ICP by reducing intracranial volume; in turn, sustained ICP elevation is a trigger for CSF drainage.
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HVICP} \\ \Leftrightarrow \\ \text{TILFever} \end{array}$	Fever raises cerebral metabolism and blood flow, which can increase ICP; uncontrolled ICP prompt aggressive management to limit metabolic demand.
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HVICP} \\ \Leftrightarrow \\ \text{TILHyperosmolarTherapy} \end{array}$	Hyperosmolar therapy lowers ICP by drawing water out of brain tissue; intracranial hypertension is the main indication for escalating therapy.
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HVICP} \\ \Leftrightarrow \\ \text{TILHyperventilation} \end{array}$	Hyperventilation reduces ICP via cerebral vasoconstriction; it is typically applied reactively in response to intracranial hypertension.
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HVICP} \\ \Leftrightarrow \\ \text{TILMannitolDose} \end{array}$	Mannitol is administered specifically to lower elevated ICP; dosing is driven by the severity and persistence of ICP elevation.
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HVICP} \\ \Leftrightarrow \\ \text{TILSedation} \end{array}$	Sedation reduces cerebral metabolic rate and prevents ICP surges; worsening ICP is a frequent reason to escalate sedation intensity.

F Informative Intensity Matrices

Figure 6 is associated with a patient with a severe TBI (Marshall CT 5), complicated by hypocapnia, treated with mannitol at low doses. The ICP is markedly unstable, with transitions out of the <15 mmHg range to the 20-25 mmHg or ≥ 25 mmHg ranges. This suggests that with hypocapnia present, the therapeutic regime is insufficient to avoid ICP excursions.

Fig. 6: ICP parameters for a patient with a Marshall CT classification of 5, one hypocapnia event and daily cumulative mannitol dose between 0-2 g.

Figure 7 is similar to the previous one, but in this case the patient does not experience any hypocapnia. Still, rapid excursions above <15 mmHg and $15-20$ mmHg are present and the sojourn time in these states is short.

Fig. 7: ICP parameters for a patient with a Marshall CT classification of 5 and daily cumulative mannitol dose between 0-2 g.

G Limitations

While the resulting model takes into account several aspects and issues related to the interaction between treatments and ICP under incomplete trajectories, there are still several limitations that must be addressed.

Lack of Comprehensive Validation. The most relevant limitation is the lack of systematic validation, both internal and external. Internal validation must be discussed in details with clinicians to define accurately reference outcomes and targets, e.g. elevated ICP time span minimization, predicted GOSE at 6 months, and more. External validation via other data sources is currently under evaluation. Moreover, another prominent limitation for CTBNs is related to the absence of standardized evaluation procedures and readily available software.

Integration of Baseline Variables. Attempts to integrate baseline variables, static patients covariates that are observed once at ICU admission, was made, see Appendix H. Still, this attempt resulted in a disconnected graph, which is typical when evidence is sparse and uncertain. A possible solution would be to adapt some approaches from existing literature on hybrid CTBNs [5, 6].

Sparsity of High-Dimensional CIMs. Another limitation is related to the sparsity of the ICP CIM due to the exponential number of treatment combinations, which hinders the scalability of the model, see Appendix I. A possible solution would be to take advantage of the clinical practice to rule out inadmissible combinations, reducing the total number of parameters.

Small Weights for Completed Trajectories. A side effect of sample-based inference techniques is that the mass of the completed trajectories tends to degenerate due to the sparsity of the evidence. There are two possible solutions: (i) apply mass correction [3] to the sampled trajectories to filter particles with low probability, or (ii) shift to *temporally uncertain* evidence that is able to model not only the uncertainty on the state, but also the uncertainty on the temporal interval, moving from a point evidence to an interval-like evidence. The former is computationally intensive, while the latter requires to manually elicit prior knowledge on the interval duration, if any.

H Integration of Baseline Variables

An attempt to model the initial distribution P^0 was done by learning a (static) Bayesian network (BN) [7] from some of the baseline variables, such as:

- HVICP_*_BIN report the minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of the ICP, binarized with a threshold of 22 mmHg.
- EDArrival* measure vitals at arrival, e.g. EDArrivalpH is the pH at arrival.
- EDComplEvent* are second insults related to the pre-hospital and ER phase, e.g. EDComplEventCardArr whether the patient suffered cardiac arrest.
- Other variables can be found in the interactive version of the *data dictionary* (i.e. lookup table) at: <https://www.center-tbi.eu/data/dictionary>.

However, as reported in Figure 8, these variables are mostly disconnected from ICP, most probably due the low sample size and high-dimensionality of the initial distribution. The only exception is **Age**, which is reported in the clinical literature to impact the morphology of ICP waveform [8]. More work is needed to elicit prior knowledge and develop techniques capable of mixing static and dynamic variables in CTBNs efficiently.

Fig. 8: Static model with baseline variables. High-resolution figure, zoom in to inspect labels and arrows.

I Sparsity of High-Dimensional CIMs

The histogram of the frequency of values of Jeffreys divergence for $\mathbf{Q}_{\text{ICP}|\Pi_{\text{ICP}}}$ is reported in Figure 9. The closer the value is to zero, the closer the IM is to the non-informative prior. For values exactly equal to zero the IM is the prior, which means that there are no observed trajectories for that specific parents combination. The CIM is quite sparse, with more than a thousand zeros out of a total of 1728 combinations.

Fig. 9: Histogram of Jeffreys divergence values for $\mathbf{Q}_{\text{ICP}|\Pi_{\text{ICP}}}$. Absolute frequencies on the y-axis are reported in logarithmic scale.

References

- [1] Uri Nodelman et al. “Expectation maximization and complex duration distributions for continuous time Bayesian networks”. In: *Proceedings of the 21st Conference on Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence, UAI 2005*. 2005.
- [2] Yu Fan et al. “Importance sampling for continuous time Bayesian networks”. In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 11 (2010).
- [3] Liessman Sturlaugson et al. “Uncertain and negative evidence in continuous time Bayesian networks”. In: *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning* 70 (Mar. 2016).
- [4] Christian R. Shelton et al. “Tutorial on structured continuous-time markov processes”. In: *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research* 51 (2014).
- [5] Carlos Villa-Blanco et al. “Multidimensional continuous time Bayesian network classifiers”. In: *International Journal of Intelligent Systems* 36.12 (2021).

- [6] Carlos Villa-Blanco et al. “Constraint-based and hybrid structure learning of multidimensional continuous-time Bayesian network classifiers”. In: *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning* 159 (Aug. 2023).
- [7] Hector Geffner et al., eds. *Probabilistic and Causal Inference*. New York, NY, USA: ACM, Feb. 2022.
- [8] Magdalena Kasprowicz et al. “Impact of age and mean intracranial pressure on the morphology of intracranial pressure waveform and its association with mortality in traumatic brain injury”. In: *Critical Care* 29.1 (Feb. 2025).